

Design, Synthesis and In-Silico Evaluation Of 2-Alkyl/Aryl,5- Substituted Aryl 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Derivatives as Potential Anti-Alzheimer Agents

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD), a neurodegenerative disorder marked by cognitive decline, remains a significant therapeutic challenge. This study aimed to design, synthesize, and evaluate novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives as potential nootropic agents inspired by the activity profile of Piracetam. A library of 30 compounds (PS-1 to PS-30) was designed and screened using in-silico tools including PASS Online, Swiss ADME, ProTox-III, and molecular docking (Molsoft.icm-pro.v3.8.3). Ten compounds were synthesized based on predicted nootropic activity, blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, bioavailability, and low toxicity. Docking scores for these compounds ranged from -21 to -25 kcal/mol, outperforming Piracetam (-21 kcal/mol), while SwissADME and ProTox-III confirmed favorable ADME and safety profiles. These findings highlight the therapeutic potential of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives as nootropic agents and support their further development in the treatment of AD and related cognitive disorders.

Keywords: 1,3,4-Oxadiazole, Alzheimer's disease, Nootropic agents, Molecular docking, Blood-brain barrier, In-silico screening.

INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent form of dementia is Alzheimer's disease (AD), which is named after the German psychiatrist Alois Alzheimer. It is a slowly progressing neurodegenerative condition marked by neuritic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles caused by the buildup of amyloid-beta peptide ($A\beta$) in the medial temporal lobe, the most affected area of the brain, as well as neocortical structures. Currently, there are about 50 million AD patients worldwide; by 2050, this number is expected to double every five years, reaching 152 million.⁽¹⁾

PATHOGENESIS

Many theories have emerged to explain the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease, but due to its complexity, no single theory has been clearly defined. There are two types of AD: sporadic forms (which make up more than 95%) and familial forms (which make up 1–5% of cases).⁽²⁾

The main neuropathological characteristics of Alzheimer's disease (AD) include the accumulation of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) in the brain parenchyma and cerebral vasculature, the presence of intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles, and progressive synaptic loss. Still, the exact causes responsible for disease initiation and progression remain unknown. According to the Tau protein hyperphosphorylation hypothesis, one of the main causes of AD is neurofibrillary tangles, which are created when Tau proteins are hyperphosphorylated. Tau proteins were initially linked to dementia due to their presence in plaques observed in the brains of Alzheimer's disease (AD) patients.⁽³⁾

In Alzheimer's disease (AD), there is a significant loss of neurons, particularly in regions responsible for memory and higher cognitive functions. Mature neurones in the healthy adult brain use complex mechanisms to prevent cell death signalling from being activated. these defenses are disrupted in AD, which leads to abnormal activation of multiple types of regulated cell death.⁽⁴⁾

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Oxadiazole:

Oxadiazoles are heterocyclic compounds consisting of a five-membered ring containing one oxygen and two nitrogen atoms. Numerous techniques for the synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been reported in the literature. One of the most common approaches involves the reaction of acid hydrazides (or hydrazine derivatives) with acid-dehydrating agents such as phosphorus oxychloride, thionyl chloride, phosphorus pentoxide, triflic anhydride, polyphosphoric acid, or direct conversion of acids to (N-isocyanimino)

triphenylphosphorane intermediates. In the development of antidepressant medications, derivatives with a 1,3,4-oxadiazole structure are commonly used. Several 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have demonstrated potent antidepressant properties.⁽⁵⁾

Chemistry of oxadiazoles

oxadiazoles exist in different isomeric forms, e.g., 1,3,4-oxadiazole, 1,2,3-oxadiazole, 1,2,4-oxadiazole and 1,2,5-oxadiazole

Figure No.1: Isomeric forms of Oxadiazole.⁽⁶⁾

Drugs having nootropic activity.

Table No.1: Name of drugs show nootropic activity

Sr. No	Drugs	Pharmacological activity
1.	<p style="text-align: center;">Donepezil.⁽⁷⁾</p>	Nootropic
2.	<p style="text-align: center;">Tacrine.⁽⁸⁾</p>	Nootropic
3.	<p style="text-align: center;">Pyritinol.⁽⁹⁾</p>	Nootropic
4.	<p style="text-align: center;">Rivastigmine.⁽¹⁰⁾</p>	Nootropic

5.	<p>Galantamine.⁽¹¹⁾</p>	Nootropic
6.	<p>Piracetam.⁽¹²⁾</p>	Nootropic
7.	<p>Memantine.⁽¹³⁾</p>	Nootropic

Piracetam

In 1967, Piracetam (2-pyrrolidone acetamide) was developed to enhance memory and learning while minimizing cognitive impairment⁽¹⁴⁾⁽¹⁵⁾. Its nootropic mechanism involves the reduction of acetylcholinesterase activity, neuroinflammatory

mediators, pro-apoptotic proteins, and oxidative stress in the cerebral environment.⁽¹⁶⁾

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Design library of compounds

Table No.2: Design of Library of compounds

<p>PS-1</p> <p>4,4'-(1,3,4-oxadiazole-2,5-diyl)dianiline</p>		
<p>PS-4</p> <p>2-[5-(4-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]benzene-1,4-diol</p>		
<p>PS-7</p>		

4-(5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)aniline	[5-(4-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]aniline	3-[5-(4-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]aniline
<p>PS-10</p> <p>PS-12 {3-[5-(4-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]-5-nitrophenyl}(hydroxy)oxoammonium</p>		
<p>PS-13</p> <p>4-[5-(3-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]aniline</p>		
<p>PS-16</p> <p>2-[5-(4-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]benzene-1,3-diol</p>		
<p>PS-19</p> <p>4-(5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)aniline</p>		
<p>PS-22</p> <p>3-(5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)aniline</p>		

<p>PS-25</p> <p>PS-27 2-methyl-5-[(E)-2-phenylethenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole</p>		
<p>PS-28</p> <p>PS-30 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole</p>		

Pass Online

PASS (Prediction of Activity Spectra for Substances) is a computer-aided software program that predicts the biological activity spectrum of a compound based on its chemical structure. The predictions are generated using structure-activity relationship (SAR) data derived from a set of over 250,000 biologically active compounds, including drugs, drug-like molecules, leads, and toxic substances. (pdf) The probability that the predicted compound falls into the category of active compounds is assessed by Pa (probability "to be active"), and the probability of falling into the category of inactive compounds is assessed by Pi (probability "to be inactive").⁽¹⁷⁾

Swiss ADME

Swiss ADME is an online resource that provides free access to a collection of reliable predictive models for pharmacokinetics, physicochemical characteristics, druglikeness, and medicinal chemistry friendliness. It is the first web-based tool that allows multiple-molecule ADME calculations, enabling chemical library analysis and effective lead optimisation.⁽¹⁸⁾

Protox 3.0

ProTox 3.0 uses machine learning models, pharmacophore-based approaches, fragment propensities, and molecular similarity to predict various toxicity endpoints. It is a publicly available computational toxicity prediction platform that

incorporates 61 models, making it one of the most comprehensive tools for toxicity prediction. The ProTox webserver features a unique prediction scheme that encompasses multiple toxicity levels, including oral toxicity, organ toxicity (hepatotoxicity, neurotoxicity, respiratory toxicity, cardiotoxicity, and nephrotoxicity), and toxicological endpoints (mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, BBB-permeability, ecotoxicity, clinical toxicity, and nutritional toxicity).⁽¹⁹⁾

Molecular docking

Molecular docking examines various mechanisms by which agonists bind to specific biological receptors, often proteins. Understanding the ligand-receptor binding mechanism helps predict the binding affinity of an agonist (drug). Molecular docking is commonly used to computationally screen large chemical libraries in the early stages of drug discovery. It predicts non-covalent molecular interactions, such as those between a ligand and a protein receptor.⁽²⁰⁾

Ligand Preparation

The chemical structures of the designed 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives were drawn using ACD/ChemSketch, and the structures were saved in mol format. These 2D structures were then imported into Molsoft ICM-Pro, where they were converted into 3D conformations. Each ligand was protonated at physiological pH 7.4 and energy minimized using the

MMFF94 force field to obtain a stable and low-energy structure suitable for docking.

Protein Preparation

The crystal structure of acetylcholinesterase (PDB ID: 4PQE) was retrieved from the RCSB sProtein Data Bank. The protein was prepared in ICM-Pro by removing water molecules, correcting any missing side chains or atoms, and adding hydrogen atoms. The structure was then minimized to remove any strain in the structure. The active site was identified based on the position of the co-crystallized ligand present in the crystal structure.⁽²¹⁾

Docking Procedure

Molecular docking was carried out using the flexible docking algorithm of Molsoft ICM-Pro. A grid map was generated around the binding site, and each ligand was flexibly docked using biased probability Monte Carlo (BPMC) sampling. Multiple binding poses were generated for each ligand. Docking scores were calculated based on binding energy, and the top-scoring poses were selected based on their orientation and interactions within the active site of acetylcholinesterase.⁽²²⁾

PROTEIN DATA AND ACTIVE SITE:

Crystal Structure of Human Acetylcholinesterase (4PQE)

Figure no.2: Image of protein Ach esterase

Acetylcholinesterase interacts with ligands through key regions such as the active site (Ser203, His447, Glu334), anionic site (Trp86, Tyr133, Glu202), acyl binding site (Trp236, Phe295, Phe297), and oxyanion site (Gly121, Gly122). The anionic subsite and omega loop region (Trp286, Tyr337, and Thr83) also play crucial roles. Notably, Trp286 is essential for ligand binding and inhibition of enzyme activity.^(23, 24)

SYNTHETIC SCHEME AND PROCEDURE

From our study, we have identified compounds PS-1, PS-4, PS-6, PS-7, PS-8, PS-10, PS-11, PS-13, PS-14 and PS-18 for further investigation due to their superior performance in Pass online, SwissADME, ProTox III, and molecular docking evaluations compared to other compounds. These identified compounds demonstrated outstanding results in terms of drug-likeness, ADMET properties, toxicity predictions, and molecular interactions, making them promising candidates for subsequent research and development. For this reason we have selected PS-1, PS-4, PS-6, PS-7, PS-8, PS-10, PS-11, PS-13, PS-14 and PS-18 compounds which was synthesized in laboratory

Synthesis of PABA hydrazide from benzocaine

Ethyl p-aminobenzoate (0.1 mol) and 100% hydrazine hydrate (0.2 mol) were melted in a closed container. (110°C, 90 min). Recrystallization from ethanol yielded intermediate hydrazide.⁽²⁵⁾

Method for synthesis of (PS-1) 4-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)aniline

A Mixture of Aromatic Acid (Benzoic acid) (0.5mole) and 4 amino benzohydrazide (0.5mole) was placed in round bottom flask, to it, POCl₃ (1mole) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 30 min. It was allowed to cool to room temperature. To it water (15

ml) was added dropwise in fume hood and the contents were further refluxed for 3-4 Hr. then contents were allowed to cool to room temperature and basified with 0.1M KOH Solution. The precipitate obtained was filtered and recrystallized with Ethanol. The reaction was monitored by TLC using Mobile Phase Toluene: Ethyl Acetate: Glacial acetic acid (7:3:1).⁽²⁶⁾

Similarly other derivatives were prepared using aromatic acids namely Benzoic acid, Gallic acid, Anthranilic acid), (Para-amino benzoic acid), 2,6-

dihydroxybenzoic acid, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid, Cinnamic acid.

Table No.3: Structures of Synthesized Compounds with Assigned Code Numbers

Compound code	Structure	Compound code	Structure
PS-1		PS-10	
PS-4		PS-11	
PS-6		PS-13	
PS-7		PS 14	
PS-8		PS-18	

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of thirty novel 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole derivatives were successfully designed and structurally prepared using chem sketch software. These compounds were then subjected to a series of in silico evaluations

including activity prediction, ADME profiling, toxicity, and molecular docking.

In-silico evaluation of pharmacological profile of designed molecules (pass online)

Table no.4: Biological activities determined by using Pass online

Sr. No	Compound code	Biological activity	Pass online	Pass online
1	PS-1	Nootropic	0,584	0,084
2	PS-2	Nootropic	0,532	0,351
3	PS-3	Nootropic	0,590	0,081
4	PS-4	Nootropic	0,356	0,263
5	PS-5	Nootropic	0,515	0,121
6	PS-6	Nootropic	0,382	0,234
7	PS-7	Nootropic	0,536	0,109
8	PS-8	Nootropic	0,459	0,165
9	PS-9	Nootropic	0,566	0,093
10	PS-10	Nootropic	0,563	0,094
11	PS-11	Nootropic	0,547	0,102
12	PS-12	Nootropic	0,577	0,087
13	PS-13	Nootropic	0,374	0,242
14	PS-14	Nootropic	0,563	0,094
15	PS-15	Nootropic	0,533	0,111
16	PS-16	Nootropic	0,521	0,118
17	PS-17	Nootropic	0,541	0,106
18	PS-18	Nootropic	0,412	0,204
19	PS-19	Nootropic	0,398	0,218
20	PS-20	Nootropic	0,111	0,265
21	PS-21	Nootropic	0,342	0,281
22	PS-22	Nootropic	0,348	0,273
23	PS-23	Nootropic	0,358	0,260
24	PS-24	Nootropic	0,535	0,109
25	PS-25	Nootropic	0,337	0,287
26	PS-26	Nootropic	0,342	0,281
27	PS-27	Nootropic	0,388	0,090
28	PS-28	Nootropic	0,384	0,143
29	PS-29	Nootropic	0,380	0,080
30	PS-30	Nootropic	0,314	0,122
	Piracetam	Nootropic	0,876	0,008

Based on PASS prediction, compounds PS-1, PS-3, PS-9, PS-10, PS-11, PS-12, PS-13, PS-14 and PS-17 showed the highest probability ($P_a > 0.56$) for nootropic activity, indicating promising potential. 2-alkyl 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives PS-19 to PS-30 have less Nootropic potential as

compared to 2-aryl 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives.

In-silico evaluation of Pharmacokinetic property of designed molecules. (SWISS ADME software)

Table no.5: ADME Prediction of synthesized compound by Swiss ADME Software.

Compounds code	Molecular weight	LipophilicityConsensus log o/w	Water solubility	GI Absorption	BBB	Bioavailability score
PS-1	222.24	2.59	-3.38	High	Yes	0.55
PS-2	238.24	2.17	-3.23	High	No	0.55
PS-3	270.24	2.04	-3.01	High	No	0.55

PS-	237.26	1.45	-2.20	High	Yes	0.55
PS-5	237.26	1.37	-2.19	High	No	0.55
PS-6	238.24	1.78	-3.06	High	No	0.55
PS-7	254.24	1.78	-3.06	High	No	0.55
PS-8	286.24	2.05	-3.12	High	No	0.55
PS-9	253.26	2.04	-3.23	High	No	0.55
PS-10	253.26	2.50	-3.23	High	No	0.55
PS-11	270.24	1.85	-3.28	High	Yes	0.55
PS-12	286.24	2.23	-3.12	High	No	0.55
PS-13	318.24	1.10	-2.82	Low	No	0.55
PS-14	285.25	1.55	-2.91	High	Yes	0.55
PS-15	285.25	1.36	-2.91	High	No	0.55
PS-16	237.26	2.37	-3.38	High	Yes	0.55
PS-17	253.26	1.97	-3.23	High	No	0.55
PS-18	285.25	1.36	-2.91	High	No	0.55
PS-19	252.27	2.07	-3.01	High	No	0.55
PS-20	252.27	2.02	-3.01	High	No	0.55
PS-21	176.17	2.00	-2.41	High	Yes	0.55
PS-22	162.15	1.60	-2.13	High	Yes	0.55
PS-23	190.20	2.31	-2.66	High	Yes	0.55
PS-24	204.23	2.51	-2.87	High	Yes	0.55
PS-25	284.27	2.63	-3.48	High	No	0.55
PS-26	328.32	3.32	-3.73	High	No	0.55
PS-27	266.30	2.24	-3.30	High	No	0.55
PS-28	234.21	1.47	-2.04	High	No	0.56
PS-29	270.24	1.66	-3.28	High	No	0.55
PS-30	270.24	1.90	-3.28	High	No	0.55
Piracetam	142.16	0.79	-0.38	High	No	0.55

the pharmacokinetic properties of compounds (PS-1 to PS-30) was evaluated and evaluation of Water solubility, GI absorption, and affinity to cross Blood brain barrier is studied along with Bioavailability. PS-1, PS-4, PS -11, PS-16, PS-21, PS-22, PS-23, PS-24

shows better crossing of blood brain barrier as compare to Piracetam.

In-silico evaluation of pharmacological toxicity of designed molecules. (PROTOX-III)

Table no.6: Toxicity profiles of designed derivative by Protox-III

Compound code	Predicted LD50 (mg/kg)	Predicted Accuracy %	Hepato toxicity	Carcinogenicity	Immuno toxicity	Mutagenicity	Cytotoxicity
PS-1	2000	72.9	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-2	2032	72.9	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-3	2000	72.9	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-4	2000	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-5	2412	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-6	2032	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-7	2300	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-8	1260	72.9	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-9	2000	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-10	2412	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-11	2412	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Active
PS-12	2604	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Active

PS-13	2000	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-14	2500	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-15	2500	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-16	2500	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-17	2000	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-18	2032	70.90	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-19	888	72.90	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-20	2032	72.90	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-21	2000	72.90	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-22	2032	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-23	2032	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-24	1704	70.97	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-25	2032	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-26	2032	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-27	888	69.26	active	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-28	888	69.26	active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-29	888	69.26	active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
PS-30	888	69.26	active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Piracetam	2000	100	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive

The predicted toxicity class is based on Globally Harmonized System (GHS) criteria, which classifies compounds into six classes:

- Class I: Extremely toxic ($LD_{50} \leq 5$ mg/kg)
 - Class II: Highly toxic ($LD_{50} > 5-50$ mg/kg)
 - Class III: Moderately toxic ($LD_{50} > 50-300$ mg/kg)
 - Class IV: Slightly toxic ($LD_{50} > 300-2000$ mg/kg)
 - Class V: Practically non-toxic ($LD_{50} > 2000-5000$ mg/kg)
 - Class VI: Non-toxic ($LD_{50} > 5000$ mg/kg)
- Among the designed compounds the most toxic compounds are PS-19, PS-27, PS-28, PS-29, and PS-30 with $LD_{50} = 888$ mg/kg.
 - The least toxic compound is PS-12 with $LD_{50} = 2604$ mg/kg.
 - Most other compounds have LD_{50} values ranging from 1260 mg/kg to 2500 mg/kg.
 - Piracetam has an LD_{50} of 2000 mg/kg and is inactive in all toxicity categories.
 - Some compounds (PS-2, PS-6, PS-18, PS-20, PS-22, PS-23, PS-25, PS-26) have a slightly better LD_{50} (2032 mg/kg).

Molecular Docking score of library of compound

Molsoft.icm-pro.v3.8.3 software

Table no.7: Molecular Docking score of library of compound

PS-1	-21	SS-8	-21	PS-15	-22	PS-22	-9	PS-29	-6
PS-2	-19	SS-9	-23	PS-16	-23	PS-23	-11	PS-30	-11
PS-3	-24	SS-10	-18	PS-17	-21	PS-24	-3	Piracetam	-21
PS-4	-5	PS-11	-23	PS-18	-22	PS-25	-9		
PS-5	-22	PS-12	-22	PS-19	-21	PS-26	-4		
PS-6	-22	PS-13	-9	PS-20	-22	PS-27	-10		

PS-7	-22	PS-14	-25	PS-21	-11	PS-28	-8		
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- PS-14 (-25 kcal/mol) exhibits the strongest binding affinity, suggesting it has the best potential for interaction with the target protein.
- PS-24 (-3 kcal/mol) has the weakest binding, making it the least favorable candidate.
- Several compounds, including PS-3, PS-11, PS-16, and PS-18, PS-1 perform better than Piracetam (-21 kcal/mol), indicating their potential as stronger binders.

Table No:9. Molecular Docking of Ligands interacting with surrounding residues

Ligands	Surrounding residues	Dock score
PS-1	TYR:341;ASP:74;HOH:606;TRP:86;HOH:603;TYR:337;TRP:286;TYR:124	-21
PS-2	LEU:289;SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:337;TYR:124;VAL:294;TRP:286	-19
PS-3	TYR:341;ASP:74;HOH:606;GLU:202;HOH:603;TRP:86;TYR:337;TYR:124;TRP:286	-24
PS-4	TYR:337;ASP:74;TRP:86;TYR:341;TYR:124;TRP:286	-5
PS-5	VAL:294;LEU:289;TRP:286;TYR:124;TYR:337;TYR:341;SER:293	-22
PS-6	ASP:74;TYR:341;TRP:286;TYR:124;TRP:86;HOH:606;HIS:447;HOH:603;TYR:337	-22
PS-7	VAL:294;TRP:286;SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:124;TYR:337	-22
PS-8	TYR:341;TYR:337;TYR:124;SER:293;TRP:286;VAL:294	-21
PS-9	TYR:341;TYR:337;TYR:124;SER:293;TRP:286;VAL:294	-23
PS-10	TYR:337;HOH:606;GLU:202;HOH:603;TRP:86;TYR:124;SER:125;TYR:72	-18
PS-11	SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:124;TYR:72;TRP:286;LEU:289;VAL:294	-23
PS-12	ASP:74;TRP:286;TYR:341;TYR:337;GLY:121;TRP:86;HOH:603;HOH:606	-22
PS-13	ASP:74;TYR:341;SER:293	-9
PS-14	TRP:286;LEU:289;VAL:294;SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:124;TYR:337	-25
PS-15	LEU:289;VAL:294;SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:337;TYR:124;TRP:286	-22
PS-16	ASP:74;TYR:341;TRP:286;TYR:124;TYR:337;HOH:603;TRP:86;HOH:606	-23
PS-17	SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:124;TYR:337;VAL:294;TRP:286;LEU:289	-21
PS-18	VAL:294;TRP:286;SER:293;TYR:341;TYR:124;TYR:337	-22
PS-19	TRP:286;TRP:86;ASP:74;TYR:341;TYR:337;TYR:124	-21
PS-20	TYR:124;SER:125;TRP:86;HOH:606;HOH:603	-22
PS-21	TYR:337;ASP:74;TRP:86;TYR:341;TYR:124;TRP:286	-11
PS-22	GLU:202;HOH:606;SER:125;TYR:124;HOH:603;TRP:86	-9
PS-23	HOH:606;HIS:447;HOH:603;TRP:86;TYR:337;TYR:124;SER:125	-11
PS-24	SER:125;HOH:606;TRP:86;HOH:603;TYR:337;TYR:124	-3
PS-25	TYR:341;SER:125;HOH:606;GLY:448;GLU:202;HOH:603;TRP:86;TYR:337;TYR:124;	-9
PS-26	TRP:26;HOH:606;SER:125;TYR:124	-4
PS-27	TYR:72;HOH:603;TRP:86;HOH:606;SER:125;TYR:124	-10
PS-28	TYR:124;TYR:337;HOH:606;HOH:603;TRP:86	-8
PS-29	TYR:337;HOH:603;HOH:606;TYR:124;SER:125;TRP:86	-6
PS-30	TYR:124;TRP:86;HIS:447;HOH:606;SER:125	-11
PIRACETAM	GLU:185;HOH:604;LYS:53;ASN:186;TRP:182	-21

Molecular Docking using Molecular Modeling.

Table no. 10: Molecular Docking and 2D, 3D images of Interaction by using Biovia

Compound Code	Dock score (Kcal/mol)	2D Molecular Visualization	3D Molecular Visualization
PS-1	-21		
PS-2	-19		
PS-3	-24		
PS-4	-5		

<p>PS-5</p> <p>-22</p>		
<p>PS-6</p> <p>-22</p>		
<p>PS-7</p> <p>-22</p>		
<p>PS-8</p> <p>-21</p>		
<p>PS-9</p> <p>-23</p>		

PS-15	-22		
PS-16	-23		
PS-17	-21		
PS-18	-22		
PS-19	-21		

PS-20	-22		
PS-21	-11		
PS-22	-9		
PS-23	-11		
PS-24	-3		

PS-25	-9		
PS-26	-4		
PS-27	-10		
PS-28	-8		
PS-29	-6		

Synthetic Work and spectral characterization of synthesized comp

PS-1 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O$, molecular weight: 237.26. Appearance: white solid, melting point 131 °C. IR: 3429.78 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 3033.48 cm^{-1} (Ar–H stretch), 1681.62 cm^{-1} (C=N, oxadiazole), 1626.66 cm^{-1} (N–H bending), 1171.54 cm^{-1} (C–O, oxadiazole), 842.74 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 10.58 (2H, broad singlet, –NH₂), 7.96 (2H, doublet, aromatic CH), 7.63 (1H, triplet, aromatic CH), 7.52 (2H, doublet, aromatic CH), 6.53 (2H, doublet, aromatic CH).

PS-4 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$, molecular weight: 269.26. Brown solid, melting point 143 °C. IR: 3465.46 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 1704.76 cm^{-1} (C=N, oxadiazole), 3055.66 cm^{-1} (Ar–H stretching), 1071.26 cm^{-1} (C–O, oxadiazole), 705.819 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.73 (2H, ddd), 6.88 (1H, dd), 7.26 (1H, dd), 7.58–7.77 (3H, multiplet, aromatic).

PS-6 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$, molecular weight: 269.26. Red-brown solid, melting point 152 °C. IR: 3306.36 cm^{-1} (O–H stretch), 3059.51 cm^{-1} (Ar–H stretch), 1697.05 cm^{-1} (C=N, oxadiazole), 1630.52 cm^{-1} (N–H bending), 1174.44 cm^{-1} (C–O, oxadiazole), 768.494 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 8.6 (1H, singlet, OH), 8.1 (1H, singlet), 7.6, 7.1, 7.0 (aromatic), 6.6 and 6.5 (2H each, aromatic), 5.7 (1H, broad singlet, NH₂).

PS-7 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$, molecular weight: 269.26. Brown solid, melting point 131 °C. IR: 3306.36 cm^{-1} (O–H stretch), 3059.51 cm^{-1} (Ar–H stretch), 1697.05 cm^{-1} (C=N), 1630.52 cm^{-1} (N–H bending), 1174.44 cm^{-1} (C–O), 768.494 cm^{-1} (Ar–H

bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.45 (1H, triplet), 6.74 (2H, ddd), 7.48 (2H, dd), 7.67 (2H, ddd).

PS-8 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{12}N_4O$, molecular weight: 252.28. White solid, melting point 149 °C. IR: 3289 cm^{-1} (N–H/Ar–H stretch), 1699.94 cm^{-1} (C=N), 1288.22 cm^{-1} (C–O), 748.245 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.67–6.83 (3H, multiplet), 7.35–7.56 (2H, multiplet), 7.66–7.89 (3H, multiplet).

PS-11 - molecular formula: $C_{15}H_{13}N_3O_3$, molecular weight: 283.28. Brown solid, melting point 140 °C. IR: 3306.82 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 3033.48 cm^{-1} (O–H), 3059.3 cm^{-1} (Ar–H), 1697.19 cm^{-1} (C=N), 1630 cm^{-1} (N–H bending), 1174 cm^{-1} (C–O), 770.423 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.79 (2H, ddd), 7.23 (1H, doublet), 7.34–7.62 (6H, aromatic), 7.70 (2H, ddd).

PS-13 - molecular formula: $C_{16}H_{13}N_3O$, molecular weight: 269.26. Brown solid, melting point 143 °C. IR: 3649.62 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 1698.02 cm^{-1} (C=N and C=C), 1281.47 cm^{-1} (C–O), 686.534 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.79 (2H, ddd), 7.23 (1H, doublet), 7.34–7.62 (6H, aromatic), 7.70 (2H, ddd).

PS-14 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{10}ClN_3O$, molecular weight: 271.70. White solid, melting point 151 °C. IR: 3347.82 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 3065.3 cm^{-1} (Ar–H stretch), 1693.19 cm^{-1} (C=N), 1279.54 cm^{-1} (C–O), 770.423 cm^{-1} (Ar–H bending), 696.177 cm^{-1} (C–Cl stretch). 1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.60 (2H, singlet, –NH₂), 7.10 (1H, doublet), 6.80 (2H, doublet), 7.40 (1H, triplet), 7.60 (2H, doublet), 7.20 (2H, doublet).

PS-18 - molecular formula: $C_{14}H_{11}N_3O_3$, molecular weight: 269.26. Dark red solid, melting point 125 °C. IR: 3429.78 cm^{-1} (N–H stretch), 3033.48 cm^{-1} (Ar–H

stretch), 1681.62 cm^{-1} (C=N), 2675.75 cm^{-1} (O-H, carboxylic acid), 1171.54 cm^{-1} (C-O), 842.74 cm^{-1} (Ar-H bending). ^1H NMR (δ , ppm): 6.72 (2H, ddd), 6.98 (2H, dd), 7.46 (1H, triplet), 7.71 (2H, ddd).

CONCLUSION

A library of 30 novel 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives was designed and evaluated through comprehensive in-silico studies including PASS Online, SwissADME, Protox-III, and molecular docking using Molsoft. Based on these evaluations, 10 derivatives were selected for synthesis.

PASS prediction indicated promising nootropic activity, while Protox-III toxicity analysis revealed

acceptable safety profiles, with PS-12 being the least toxic ($\text{LD}_{50} = 2604 \text{ mg/kg}$), and all three selected compounds showing toxicity levels comparable to or better than Piracetam ($\text{LD}_{50} = 2000 \text{ mg/kg}$).

SwissADME analysis confirmed that PS-1, PS-11, and PS-14 have blood-brain barrier permeability, gastrointestinal absorption, and favorable bioavailability parameters. Molecular docking studies revealed that PS-14 (-25 kcal/mol), PS-11 (-23 kcal/mol), and PS-1 possess stronger binding affinities than Piracetam (-21 kcal/mol), indicating higher potential for interaction with the target proteins.

PS-1

PS-11

PS-14

Piracetam

2-alkyl 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives PS-19 to PS-30 have less Nootropic potential and more toxicity potential as compared to 2-aryl 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives. Among 2-aryl 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, 2-(4-amino phenyl) 5-substituted aryl 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives i.e. PS-1, PS-11, and PS-14 are promising lead candidates for further development as potential nootropic agent which would be useful as anti-alzheimer agents.

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